

1 From heat wave Zoe to heat wave Vera: a two-year ex post evaluation of the 2 categorization and naming heat wave system ProMeteo in Seville, Spain

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28 The heat wave *Zoe* in Seville (Spain) (July 24th, 2022) was the first heat wave event
29 named after a health-based categorization system. It was followed in 2023 by their
30 siblings *Yago*, *Xenia*, *Wenceslao*, and *Vera*.

31 We report here how the pilot project ProMeteo addressed the forecast, and the main
32 climatic characteristics of the heat waves identified during those years. We also provided
33 a comparison between model expectations and observed daily mortality.

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44 Heat waves have been identified since the late 20th century and early 21st century as hazardous events with strong
45 negative impact on health, including premature mortality(Becker *et al.*, 2022; Campbell *et al.*, 2018; Sheridan and
46 Allen, 2018; Sheridan *et al.*, 2021). Among other heat waves, the European heat wave of 2003, in which it's estimated
47 that over 70 000 people died, was pivotal in motivating efforts to mitigate the societal impact of heat waves(Robine

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48 *et al.*, 2008), especially as the frequency and intensity of heat waves are projected to increase during the coming
 49 years(IPCC, 2021; King and Karoly, 2017; Masson-Delmotte *et al.*, 2021; Perkins, 2015).

50 In this line, the Adrienne Arsht-Rockefeller Foundation Resilience Center at the Atlantic Council, in collaboration
 51 with international climate and health experts in the United States and in Seville, Spain, embarked on an effort to
 52 develop and pilot the use of a synoptic heat wave categorization system based on forecast local excess mortality,
 53 rather than meteorological variables alone. The categorization system was initially implemented in summer 2022 as
 54 a pilot evaluation in six cities, including four system demonstrations in the U.S. (Kansas City, Los Angeles, Miami,
 55 Milwaukee) and two publicly communicated pilots in Europe (Seville, Spain and Athens, Greece). In Seville, the pilot
 56 was given a public facing name – ProMeteo. In partnership with Seville City Council, ProMeteo tested a naming
 57 protocol for heat waves to increase awareness and facilitate communication among citizens and public officials, making
 58 Zoe the first ever named heat wave in July 2022. Seville was the only city to implement naming of high category
 59 heat waves as part of an awareness and communications strategy that mimics the standard protocol for storms and
 60 other hazardous tropospheric phenomena. If a heat wave reached a predefined category based on excess mortality
 61 projection, the Seville pilot system issued a name for the heat wave. Incidentally, the start of this pilot system
 62 coincided with the notable heat wave that swept Western Europe during the summer of 2022(Copernicus, 2022a,b)
 63 which has been associated with excess mortality(Ballester *et al.*, 2023). The hot 2022 was followed by an even
 64 hotter summer in 2023.(Copernicus, 2023, 2024) The Spanish National Meteorological Office (AEMET) reports for
 65 the province of Seville two heat waves in 2022 and three heat waves in 2023.(AEMET, 2023)

66 Previously, we reported the impact of the naming system in beliefs and behaviours of residents(Metzger *et al.*, 2024)
 67 and a retrospective analysis of the correlation between excess heat and excess mortality in the city of Seville(Kalkstein
 68 *et al.*, 2024)

69 The goal of this paper is to present an evaluation of how well this novel system performed in 2022 and in 2023 in
 70 order to provide insights and suggestions for continued improvement of the system.

71 The municipality of Seville (37.24° North, 5.99° West, population 681 998 as of January 1 2022 (Royal Decree
 72 1037/2022), area 140 km², elevation 7 m) and the surrounding Seville province (NUTS code ES618, population
 73 1 948 393, area 14 000 km²) are located along the lower basin of the Guadalquivir river in Southwestern Spain (see
 74 Figure S1 in Supplementary Material). The city has a Mediterranean, temperate climate (Köppen classification Csa)
 75 characterized by a dry, hot summer(Kottke *et al.*, 2006; Tullot, 2000). For the purpose of testing a pilot system that
 76 characterizes the impact of heat waves on mortality, Seville has unique characteristics that include high summer tem-
 77 peratures and a large population—the latter being necessary for a proper statistical characterization of excess mortality
 78 associated with heat(Royé *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, Seville is the hottest major metropolitan area in Europe with
 79 frequent daily maximum temperatures above 40 °C in the summer and a record hottest temperature of 46.6 °C in
 80 1995. The city of Seville also experiences high summer heat variability associated with the prevailing winds; westerlies
 81 bring warm air masses while easterlies usually bring dry, hot air masses.

82 1. METHODS

83 The novel heat warning, categorization and naming system has been thoroughly described elsewhere(Kalkstein
 84 *et al.*, 2024). It is based on the retrospective analysis of the synoptic air masses affecting Seville since 1995 and on
 85 the impact that those air masses produced on mortality.

86 To evaluate of the performance of the system in summer 2022 we made use of the following data sets, all publicly
 87 available:

- 88 1. The daily meteorological observations at Seville Airport (LEZL) weather station (WMO 08391), operated by
 89 AEMET (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología). The series starts in 1951.
- 90 2. The 3-hour/5-day forecast available at OpenWeather for the city of Seville (city 6361046)
- 91 3. The Spanish Mortality Monitor (by Instituto de Salud Carlos III, ISC3) which produces daily estimates of the
 92 crude, all-cause deaths in Spain disaggregated by province, sex and wide age group. The series starts on January
 93 1, 2015. Hereafter the mortality monitor will be quoted as MoMo.

94 This data-set broadcasts daily an estimate of the death counts in the preceding days M , an estimate of the
 95 expected deaths E based on population, seasonality and previous death records, and a model estimate of deaths
 96 attributed to excess temperature A should daily maximum temperature overshoot a local threshold placed at
 97 40 °C(Jiménez *et al.*, 2015). Their model weights the impact of excess temperature seven days back(Nogueira
 98 and Paixão, 2008).

Category	Expected Excess Mortality	Percentile	EHF/K ²	$\sqrt{\text{EHF}}/^\circ\text{C}$
0	< 10 %	32	< 1.7	< 1.3
1	< 20 %	74	< 7.8	< 2.8
2	< 30 %	93	< 15.5	< 3.9
3	> 30 %	> 93	> 15.5	> 3.9

TABLE 1 ProMeteo Sevilla category system based on our retrospective analysis(Kalkstein *et al.*, 2024). This table lists expected excess mortality, quantile distribution of the category, excess heat factor EHF and its square root.

99 The data-set was retrieved in 2024, therefore under-reporting does not have an impact this study.

100 The severity of a heat wave in this study is defined by the Nairn-Fawcett Excess Heat Factor (EHF)(Nairn *et al.*,
101 2014). The factor combines two components of a daily characteristic temperature T :

- 102 1. The excess heat or significance index EH, which is the difference between the three-day sample moving average
103 of T and its climatological 95th percentile T_{95} :

$$\text{EH} = \text{SMA}_3 - T_{95}. \quad (1)$$

104 It measures how hot one day is in relation to the historical records of the location. For this purpose, the 95th
105 percentile of the series 1981 to 2010 was determined.

2. The acclimatization factor or index A , which is the difference between the same three-day sample moving average
and the 30-day sample moving average:

$$A = \text{SMA}_3 - \text{SMA}_{30}. \quad (2)$$

106 The acclimatization index measures how hot one day is in relation to the recent past.

The Nairn-Fawcett EHF is defined as the product of the two preceding indexes provided that EH are positive (excesses):

$$\text{EHF} = \begin{cases} \text{EH} \times \max([1^\circ\text{C}, A]), & \text{if EH positive,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

107 By construction the square root of the Nairn-Fawcett EHF is always real. It also has a simple arithmetic interpre-
108 tation: when $A \geq 1^\circ\text{C}$, the $\sqrt{\text{EHF}}$ is the geometric mean of the two indexes (EH and A). In other words $\sqrt{\text{EHF}}$ is
109 smaller than one of two indexes, and greater than the remaining index.

110 In our analysis the input of the EHF will be the daily mean apparent temperature (hereafter DMAT) which combines
111 day and night temperatures and the impact of humidity and wind(Staiger *et al.*, 2012; Steadman, 1984). The climatic
112 95th percentile of this metric in Seville was 30.8°C .

113 From 1973 to 2023 we found 527 non-zero EHF days, 11 % of the 4692 days in June, July and August. Accumulated
114 values of EHF display largest values in late July and early August (epidemiological weeks 29 to 33) when DMAT also
115 attains the highest average values, see Figure S2 in Supplementary Material. To understand the increase of average
116 temperature in the city we note that until 1982 the non-zero EHF days grew at a rate of 5.8 days per year; since 1990
117 they have grown at a rate of 13 days per year.

118 In our retrospective analysis we divided heat waves in Seville into four categories based solely on the level of
119 increased mean mortality during the event(Kalkstein *et al.*, 2024). Table 1 lists the main characteristics of each
120 category level.

121 Finally, we set a protocol to name the heat wave based on the forecast. We require a 3-day non-zero EHF series
122 with at least one Category 3 day or a 3-day accumulated EHF above 34K^2 , meaning on average a 3-day series in the
123 upper tier of Category 2. That is Category 2⁺ in Figure 1; see also Section 3.

Start date	Duration d	$\max(T_{\max})$ °C	$\max(T_{\min})$ °C	EHF_{ac} K ²	EHF_{max} K ²	Category	Name (label)	Announced
2022-Jun-11	5	42.6	23.3	13.6	4.8	1	(a)	
2022-Jul-09	3	42.5	23.0	6.9	3.7	1	(b)	
2022-Jul-13	6	44.8	26.0	45.8	13.6	2 ⁺	(c)	
2022-Jul-22	5	44.5	28.1	57.7	17.0	3	Zoe	2022-Jul-24
2022-Jul-31	4	41.0	23.9	7.5	3.0	1	(d)	
2023-Jun-24	6	42.0	23.0	77.2	23.0	3	Yago	2023-Jun-23
2023-Jul-03	2	38.2	24.3	5.4	3.2	1	(e)	
2023-Jul-10	5	41.7	25.3	27.4	8.8	2	Xenia	2023-Jul-09
2023-Jul-18	3	41.7	25.2	11.6	6.8	1	(f)	
2023-Jul-31	1	39.9	23.7	0.1	0.1	0	(g)	
2023-Aug-07	7	43.7	24.5	51.7	12.2	2 ⁺	Wenceslao	2023-Aug-07
2023-Aug-20	7	42.6	24.2	76.5	15.0	2 ⁺	Vera	2023-Aug-24

TABLE 2 Catalogue of the heat waves identified during 2022 and 2023 in Seville, Spain, with characteristics based on final observed values at the AEMET weather station. First column shows the onset date, then the duration (number of continued days), the maximum day temperature and the maximum night temperature, the accumulated EHF, the peak EHF_{max} , the category assessment, the heat wave name or label, and heat wave name announcement date. See figure 1 (top panels) for a visualization of the heat waves. Notice that the name and announcement were not based on observations, but on forecasts, see Figures S4 to S8 in Supplementary Material.

124 2. RESULTS

125 Figure 1 shows the basic observations associated with temperature (top panels) and mortality (bottom panels)
126 during the summer of 2022 (left panels) and 2023 (right panels) in Seville. The horizontal axis expands 105 days (15
127 weeks) corresponding to epidemiological week 22 to week 36.

128 Top panels in either figure shows in thin step lines SMA3 and SMA30 for the daily mean apparent temperature
129 (DMAT). The historical 95th percentile $T_{95} = 30.8^\circ\text{C}$ is noted. They also show EH (excess heat, see Eq. 1) and
130 the A (acclimatization excess, see Eq. 2) by thick step lines when they are positive. Finally the square root of the
131 Nairn-Fawcett EHF (see Eq. 3) is shown by filled steps. Excess values can be read at the right-most axis. Category
132 levels are annotated following Table 1.

133 The top panels in figure 1 show several excursions of the EHF during the summer. Each excursion makes a heat
134 wave. Unnamed events are labeled by Latin letters; else the name associated with the event is annotated. Table 2 lists
135 the primordial meteorological characteristics of the heat waves identified during 2022 and 2023: onset date, duration,
136 maximum daily temperature, the largest of the daily night temperature, the accumulated EHF, and the highest EHF
137 in the heat wave, which served to identify the category according to table 1.

138 The first heat wave in June 2022 —label (a)— came shortly before the pilot project was launched, and reached
139 category 1 (C1) in our categorization system. Thereafter, several excursions occurred along July and early August
140 2022, coincident with the heat wave that swept Western Europe (Copernicus, 2022a,b). The first excursion brought a
141 10-day series with EHF at category 1 —label (b)— and category 2 —label (c)—. After a brief, 3-day break a new heat
142 wave was onset on July 21st. The daily forecast on July 24th reached a condition to name the event (see Figure S4 in
143 Supplementary Material) and heat wave Zoe was released. It was the first named heat wave following a categorization
144 system based on the health risks.

145 Heat wave Zoe was characterized by daily maximum temperatures ranging from 44.5°C (July 25th, 11th highest
146 in records) to 40.3°C ; daily minimum temperatures from 28.1°C (July 25th, 3th highest in records) to 22.3°C ; and
147 daily mean apparent temperature ranged 34.9°C (July 25th, 22th highest in record) to 30.6°C . See table 2. Following
148 heat wave Zoe, a category 1 heat wave was observed in early August —label (d)—. In 2022 there were 23 dates with
149 non-zero EHF that accumulated 131.5K^2 .

150 In 2023, we identified seven heat waves four of which were given a name: Yago, Xenia, Wenceslao and Xenia, see
151 Table 2. Figure S5 in Supplementary Material shows the conditions when heat wave Yago was called in late June.
152 Yago was fueled by the acclimatization excess A which is usually larger during the first third of the summer, see
153 Figure 1. Heat wave Xenia and heat waves (e) and (f) occurred in early July. In retrospect, none of these heat waves
154 reached the preset condition to give a name. Those conditions existed in our forecasts, see Figure S6 in Supplementary
155 Material. The last two heat waves, Wenceslao and Vera, accumulated 14 days with excess heat were formed in early
156 August reached category 2⁺ and either of two sustained for one week, see Figures S7 and S8 in Supplementary

FIG. 1 The meteorological observations in Seville (top panels) and the observed all-cause mortality in the province of Seville (bottom panels) during the summer of 2022 (left panels) and 2023 (right panels). Dates are printed in big-endian format month/day. The top panels show the daily mean apparent temperature (DMAT, circles) its 3-day sample moving average (SMA₃) and its 30-day sample moving average (SMA₃₀) along with the climatic 95th percentile $T_{95} = 30.8^\circ\text{C}$ (left axis); the climatic excess EH (orange), the acclimatization excess A (blue), and the square root of the excess heat factor in shaded area (all excess values are read at the right axis). The dashed lines display the levels at which Category 1, 2, 3 and 4 are reached. Latin letters label unnamed heat waves. The bottom panels show the all-cause daily mortality reported by MoMo (circles M) and its 7-day central moving average (black line); the expected deaths (red line E); the expected deaths plus the deaths attributed to heat by MoMo (orange line $E + A$); and the expected deaths plus deaths attributed to EHF by our retrospective analysis (blue line, $E + C$). The darker shade shows $E \pm \sqrt{E}$ and the lighter shade shows the 1%–99% confidence interval of E as reported by MoMo. In panel A2, expected deaths are attributed by MoMo. In panel B2, MoMo expected deaths are shown by a dashed red line.

Metric	2022	2023
Observed deaths (MoMo)	4813	4271
Expected deaths (MoMo)	4426	4587
Excess deaths (MoMo)	387	-316
P -score (MoMo)	9 %	-7 %
Expected deaths (this work)	4426	3957
Excess deaths (this work)	387	314
P -score	9 %	8 %
Attributed to excess temperature (MoMo)	163	155
Attributed to EHF (this work)	111	186

TABLE 3 Mortality counts associated with epidemiological weeks 22 to 36 in Seville, Spain. See Figure 1 (bottom panels) for a visualization of the metrics.

157 Material. We report 31 dates in 2023 with non-zero EHF that accumulated 250K^2 . Compared with the previous
158 observed accumulated EHF in the series 1995 to 2023, the year 2023 is ranked the fourth hottest after 1995, 2003 and
159 2004; whereas 2022 is ranked 6th, with 1998 taking 5th place, see Figure S3 in Supplementary Material.

160 Bottom panels in Figure 1 show mortality data extracted from MoMo in the province of Seville. Data points show
161 the observed mortality with the thick black line displaying the central one-week moving average. The thick red line
162 shows the expected mortality. The darker shaded area shows the strip band $E \pm \sqrt{E}$, the expected daily deaths
163 plus/minus the square root of their expected variance. The lighter shaded area highlights the 1% – 99% confidence
164 interval of the E as reported by MoMo. The impact of meteorological variables is shown by two models. The orange
165 line shows E plus the expected deaths attributed to excess temperature as reported by MoMo. The blue lines shows
166 the excess deaths attributed to EHF by our model. (Kalkstein *et al.*, 2024)

167 Table 3 lists the basic mortality numbers associated with the 15 weeks in our analysis. In 2022 there were 4426
168 expected deaths (death rate of 23.6 deaths per day and per one million population) of which 2101 would be female
169 deaths (rate 20.2) and 2325 would be male deaths (rate 21.7). There were 4813 observed deaths (rate 23.6), 9% up
170 relative to the expected deaths, 2391 female deaths (rate 23.0, 14% up) and 2421 male deaths (rate 24.3, 4% up).

171 The observed mortality shows two excursions in 2022, see Figure 1 panel A2. The first excursion was coincidental
172 with heat wave (a) and occurred before the pilot project started. The second excursion was coincident with heat wave
173 (b), Zoe, and heat wave (c), and prolonged during July and early August.

174 Relative to the expected deaths, MoMo attributes 163 deaths (3.7%) to excess temperature, of which 124 would
175 be females and 40 would be males. Our model adds 111 (2.5%) to MoMo expected deaths.

176 In 2023 (panel B2 in Figure 1) the dashed red line shows the base expected deaths (E) reported by MoMo. The
177 full range of dates adds up 4587 expected deaths (death rate of 22.5 deaths per day per one million population) of
178 which 2231 would be female deaths (rate 21.5) and 2356 would be male deaths (rate 23.6). The observed death count
179 adds up 4271 (rate 21.0), 7% lower relative to the expected deaths, 2063 female deaths (rate 19.9, 8% lower) and
180 2209 male deaths (rate 22.1, 6% lower).

181 In view of these numbers and from a visual inspection of the dashed red line in panel B2 we removed six deaths per
182 day to the expected deaths reported by the Spanish MoMo to obtain our estimate given by the red thick line (3957
183 deaths, 19.4 per one million population). Relative to this expectations there were 314 excess deaths (8% higher).
184 MoMo excess deaths attributed to excess temperature add up 155 (4% higher than the expected mortality). Our
185 model adds 186 deaths (4.5%) to the expected deaths.

186 Figure 2 attempts to visualize the relationship between observed excess deaths and predictions by our model in
187 2022 (top) and 2023 (bottom) on a daily basis. The horizontal axis displays the EHF and the vertical axis display the
188 daily excess mortality percentage relative to the expected deaths (red line in Figure 1 bottom). The high dispersion
189 at $\text{EHF} = 0$ is attributed to the size of the model that usually lists some 45 deaths per day. Also we must take
190 into account that when a heat wave ends, deaths may accumulate in the following days, even though these days may
191 not exhibit excess heat. In 2022, daily excess deaths were consistently greater than predictions associated with heat
192 excess. Whereas in 2023 daily excess death were mostly in line with our expectations.

FIG. 2 The relationship between the daily excess heat factor (horizontal axis) and the P -score daily excess mortality (vertical axis) along with the predictions based in our model (thin line). See Table 2 for heat wave labels. Top: the year 2022. Bottom: the year 2023.

193 3. DISCUSSION

194 On 2022-Jun-21, the pilot project ProMeteo started monitoring the 5-day/3-hour forecast by OpenWeather for the
 195 city of Seville, ES and producing a systematic 5-day forecast based on the daily mean apparent temperature and the
 196 Nairn-Fawcett excess heat factor (EHF) associated with the OpenWeather data. The forecast was broadcast as a
 197 web-page that was forwarded to the partners of the project, including the City Hall. The web-page was not publicly
 198 available.

199 In Supplementary Material Figures S4 to S8 show a snapshot of the web-page with forecast close to the call of a
 200 named event. In figures S4 to S8 the top left frame lists the five categories and their associated colors: green, light
 201 orange, orange, light red, red. The right frame lists the output of the 5-day forecast, including the category level and
 202 the category color. While the forecast shows 5-day ahead, ProMeteo focused on the first three days only (D, D+1 and
 203 D+2), as the meteorological predictions tend to be more accurate in shorter terms. It must be noted that during 2022

204 the EHF was mistaken due to a miscalculation: the 30-day sample moving average was being inadvertently computed
 205 as a 50-day sample moving average. Since the categorization was based on the quantile distribution of EHF and since
 206 the miscalculation amplified the EHF systematically, the categorization system was unaffected by this mistaken.

207 ProMeteo identified two major heat waves during 2022. The first one —labeled (b) on Figure 1— started on July
 208 10th, and ended on July 21st, peaking on July 16th. It was soon followed by a second heat wave starting on July
 209 22nd, ending in July 29 and peaking in July 26th. These heat waves are concurrent with the massive heat wave that
 210 swept Europe in July 2022(Copernicus, 2022a).

211 ProMeteo warned the local authorities of the municipality of Seville of these two major heat waves and agreed
 212 with the City Council to publish a press release and other social media warnings. On July 12 ProMeteo alerted to
 213 an incoming heat wave categorized as high risk for the vulnerable population based on our retrospective analysis.
 214 Warning messages remained on social media until July 20. On July 22 a second press release warned of a new
 215 moderate heat wave for the following days. It was updated on July 23 when the risk increased to high. On July 24,
 216 the forecast predicted for the following two days DMAT 6 °C above the climatic 95th percentile (located at 30.8 °C),
 217 daily maximum temperatures seven degrees above the 95th percentile (38.2 °C) and daily minimum temperatures
 218 seven degrees above the 95th percentile (22 °C).

219 During this series of days the category 3 condition, which would have resulted in naming the event, was only attained
 220 in some forecasts during heat wave (b). At that time the partners of the project hesitated on launching a name due
 221 to, among other reasons, the novelty of the naming system, which prompted the pilot project to be cautious. Also
 222 the time difference between local partners and US partners played a role since the first forecast of the day arrived at
 223 07:00UTC (09:00 local time), midnight on the other side of the Atlantic.

224 Eventually, the conditions that had sustained since July 10 prompted the project to re-evaluate the naming criterion
 225 and the decision making process. As a result of this, it was determined on July 19 that the local partners should
 226 make the call based on the morning update. It was also agreed that a series of three days with average accumulated
 227 EHF per day in the upper tier of Category 2 should also merit a name. This level is shown by C2⁺ (category 2⁺) in
 228 Figure 1.

229 With the arrival of the early morning forecast on 2022-Jul-24 (shown in Figure S4) the new condition was satisfied,
 230 the local scientific advisor (JMM-O) made the call and the City Hall agreed to name the incoming heat wave as Zoe,
 231 following a preset alternating list of female and male proper names in reverse alphabetic order.

232 In 2023 ProMeteo identified four named events and three unnamed events. Six warning messages were broadcasts
 233 as a press release and in social media.

234 An interest point to discuss is how well the forecast performed. Figure 1 show the final observations taken at the
 235 AEMET weather station located at Seville’s Airport, 7.5 km ENE from downtown, whereas Figures S4 to S8 display
 236 the forecast condition when a named event was called. In retrospect, category 3 was effectively achieved during heat
 237 wave Zoe. Likewise, during heat wave (b) category 2⁺ condition was achieved and the heat wave (b) would have merit
 238 a name, had the protocol considered such category at that time. In 2023 heat wave Xenia was given a name based on
 239 the available forecasts (see Figure S6 in Supplementary Material) but final observations ranked the event in the lower
 240 tier of Category 2, which do not qualify for a name. The retrospective analysis of each of the remaining six events in
 241 2023 agrees with the initial call by ProMeteo including three named events —Yago, Wenceslao and Vera— and three
 242 unnamed events —labels (e), (f) and (g)—.

243 Another point of interest is readiness of our warnings. The model is based in a three-day average, which need three
 244 days to climb up. Understandably heat waves also have an uprising onset, followed by a downfall. Heat wave Zoe
 245 was announced after it had started, once the naming criterion was met. The warning was effective for the target day
 246 (2022-Jul-24), which eventually was the most dangerous of the heat wave. Heat waves Yago, Xenia and Wenceslao
 247 were identified and announced before or at their onsets. Finally, heat wave Vera was only alerted on 2023-Aug-24,
 248 four days after its onset. On Aug-21 ProMeteo launched a heat wave warning but no named event was presented,
 249 based on the available forecast which showed the accumulated EHF in the following three days in 33 K², just shy of
 250 category 2⁺. It was not until Aug-24 that the alert was upgraded and the name Vera was launched (see Figure S8).
 251 In retrospect, and based on actual observations, Aug-22 and Aug-23 attained worse conditions than those observed
 252 on Aug-24.

253 AEMET report of heat waves in the province of Seville(AEMET, 2023) differs from our story line in several ways.
 254 The heat wave (a) in June 2022 and Yago in June 2023 were not called by AEMET. Both heat waves were impacted
 255 by the acclimatization, a contribution that is missed in AEMET analysis. Second, in 2022 AEMET merged heat
 256 waves (b), (c) and Zoe in one event that started on July 9th and ended on July 26th. Also AEMET reports a heat
 257 wave from July 30 to August 14, longer than the heat wave (d) in Table 2. Finally, AEMET did not call heat waves
 258 (e), (f) and (g) in 2023, the weakest events in our catalogue.

259 Figure 1 (bottom panels) show an excursion in daily mortality synchronous with the predictions by MoMo (based

on daily maximum temperature excess) and ProMeteo’s retrospective analysis (based on the Nairn-Fawcett excess heat factor deduced from daily mean average temperature). In contrast, either model failed to estimate accurately the excess deaths in 2022. The 163 (MoMo) and 111 (ProMeteo) excess deaths are largely shy from the 387 observed excess deaths. This may be an evidence of the existence of further causes of deaths other than heat excess but, also, it is an evidence of the limitations of current models, specifically when excess heat condition prevailed during a long series of days like in July 2022 and in the context of the aftermath of the COVID-19 disease.

In 2023 the scenario was reversed and the observed death count in summer fell 7% below the expected deaths predicted by MoMo (see Figure 1 panel B2). As a plausible explanation we understand that the large excess deaths in 2022 has had an impact in the observed deaths in 2023, relative to standard models. Our educated guess of the expected deaths brings 8% excess deaths in 2023, half of which is explained by MoMo excess deaths attributed to excess temperature, and by our model.

We must emphasize that ProMeteo does not aim to accurately assess excess mortality but to early identify and categorize potential hazards so that individual and decision makers can take preemptive actions. This aim was accomplished during 2022 and 2023 since every call associated with EHF was sadly followed by a perceptible increase in mortality in line with our expectations.

The task of accurately predicting excess mortality from raw meteorological data faces the usual problem of descriptive statistics: sample size and its associated variability. Here the variability of death counts, roughly estimated as $1/\sqrt{E}$ or 20% in the province of Seville, is sizeable with the impact observed in Category 3 events. Therefore when building the relationship between EHF and excess mortality small EHF events are poorly determined because of signal noise and high EHF events due to scarcity. This scarcity suggests that the knowledge of this association is currently limited and that mismatches can happen. The analysis could be improved by considering more populated conurbations, and having a larger series of years. Alternatively, aggregated values where the total excess mortality in a summer is associated with the accumulated EHF in that season could provide further insight.

4. KNOWN LIMITATIONS

Due to the closeness between AEMET weather station and the city of Seville we assume a high correlation between temperatures at either locations. Eventually, and because the EHF is built from temperature differences (see Eq. 1 and Eq. 2), we find no reason to believe that the mismatch between the weather station and downtown has a relevant impact in our results. It must only bear in mind that our predictor is always the temperature recorded at the weather station, which plays the role of a proxy for the urban temperature.

For the lack of the daily mortality in the municipality of Seville (population 681 998 in 2022) that were used in ProMeteo’s retrospective analysis (Kalkstein *et al.*, 2024), we made use here of the daily mortality in the province of Seville (population 1 948 393 in 2022). The null hypothesis is that the ratio of the two daily death counts are roughly independent of date, and is explained by the variations in the population size. Indeed the association of the ratio versus index for the 552 dates in June, July and August from 2015 to 2020 gives Pearson’s $R^2 = 0.004$ ($p = 0.13$): the null hypothesis sustains at the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Furthermore log-log regressions of the two death counts give slope $m = 0.96[0.86, 1.06]$ with Pearson’s $R = 0.63$, and Spearman’s $R = 0.62$. The bottom line is that our predicted excess mortality P -score associated with EHF roughly applies for the mortality in the province of Seville.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented an ex post evaluation of a health-based heat wave categorization and naming system during two continued years. The monitoring system was able to forecast the major, hazardous events that hit the city of Seville during the summer of 2022 and 2023 in a timely manner.

The hazardous events were contemporaneous with spikes in daily mortality. Our predicted excess mortality based on excess heat factor (Kalkstein *et al.*, 2024) was able to explain the excess mortality observed in 2023. However, excess mortality in 2022 was worse than expectations from heat excess models.

DATA AVAILABILITY

AEMET data can be accessed by API-key from AEMET Open Data <https://opendata.aemet.es/centrodedescargas/inicio>.

308 Openweather forecast can be downloaded by API-key, see <https://openweathermap.org/api>.
 309 The Spanish daily Mortality Monitor can be downloaded at https://momo.isciii.es/panel_momo/

310 DISCLOSURES

311 Dr. Wellenius serves as a consultant to Google, LLC (Mountain View, CA) and the Health Effects Institute (Boston,
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FIG. S1 A simple map of Spain (main) with the province of Seville (ES618) in shade and the city of Seville (black circle). The bottom-right inset locates Spain in Europe. The province of Seville is 14 000 km² in surface. The city is located at coordinates 5.99° West and 37.24° North.

FIG. S2 Accumulated values of EHF per day (black, left axis) and average daily mean apparent temperature (orange, right axis) in Seville from 1973 to 2023. Date are given in epidemiological week format, from the start of week 22 to the end of week 36. The highest accumulated values and the highest average DMAT are observed from week 29 to week 33: late July to early August. Heat excess accumulated in weeks 25 and 26 are associated with larger values of the acclimatization excess, which are seldom observed elsewhere.

FIG. S3 Accumulated values of EHF per year with a whisker box on the left showing $Q_1 = 7 K^2$ (first quartile), $Q_2 = 35.8 K^2$ (second) and $Q_3 = 89.9 K^2$ (third). The whisker extends up to $Q_3 + 1.5 \times (Q_3 - Q_1) = 214.3 K^2$ to identify outliers in the distribution: the years 1995, 2003, 2004 and 2023.

Sistema de pronóstico de olas de calor para Sevilla

Nivel 3
Ola de calor de riesgo muy elevado

Nivel 2
Ola de calor de riesgo elevado

Nivel 1
Episodio de calor con impacto medio

Episodio de calor con impacto medio

Sin aviso

Fecha y hora de pronóstico 07/24/2022 09:00:01

24 7 2022	NIVEL 2
Temperatura Aparente Media	35.0 C
Temperatura Maxima	45.1 C
Temperatura Minima	25.5 C
Factor de exceso de calor	24.5
Factor de exceso de calor (total de los 3 dias siguientes)	66.5
Se recibe un nombre la onda de calor.	
Dia de calor: Temperatura maxima superior a 41 grados.	

25 7 2022	NIVEL 2
Temperatura Aparente Media	36.0 C
Temperatura Maxima	45.1 C
Temperatura Minima	29.2 C
Factor de exceso de calor	26.2
Factor de exceso de calor (total de los 3 dias siguientes)	42.8
Dia de calor: Temperatura maxima superior a 41 grados.	

26 7 2022	NIVEL 1
Temperatura Aparente Media	32.0 C
Temperatura Maxima	40.9 C
Temperatura Minima	23.1 C
Factor de exceso de calor	15.8
Factor de exceso de calor (total de los 3 dias siguientes)	16.6

27 7 2022	NIVEL 0
Temperatura Aparente Media	26.4 C
Temperatura Maxima	35.2 C
Temperatura Minima	19.6 C
Factor de exceso de calor	0.8

28 7 2022	SIN AVISO
Temperatura Aparente Media	26.3 C
Temperatura Maxima	36.8 C
Temperatura Minima	18.2 C
Factor de exceso de calor	0.0

FIG. S4 A snapshot of ProMeteo webpage when Zoe heat wave was called. on 2022-Jul-24 07:00UTC. The top left frame shows the color codes associated with every of the five categories. The right frame shows the 5-day forecast with category and color code. It must be noted that the EHF was incorrectly computed at that time. The bug did not impact the categorization system.

Sistema de pronóstico de olas de calor para Sevilla

FIG. S5 A snapshot of ProMeteo webpage when Yago heat wave was called on 2023-Jun-24 07:15UTC. The top left frame shows the color codes associated with every of the five categories. The right frame shows the 5-day forecast with category and color code.

Sistema de pronóstico de olas de calor para Sevilla

FIG. S6 A snapshot of ProMeteo webpage when Xenia heat wave was called on 2023-Jul-29 07:15UTC. The top left frame shows the color codes associated with every of the five categories. The right frame shows the 5-day forecast with category and color code.

Sistema de pronóstico de olas de calor para Sevilla

FIG. S7 A snapshot of ProMeteo webpage when Wenceslao heat wave was called on 2023-Aug-07 07:15UTC. The top left frame shows the color codes associated with every of the five categories. The right frame shows the 5-day forecast with category and color code.

Sistema de pronóstico de olas de calor para Sevilla

FIG. S8 A snapshot of ProMeteo webpage when Vera heat wave was called on 2023-Aug-24 07:30UTC. The top left frame shows the color codes associated with every of the five categories. The right frame shows the 5-day forecast with category and color code.